

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUGGESTIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of developing suggestive competence of future primary school teachers, the methodological system of developing suggestive competence of future primary school teachers, the effectiveness of developing suggestive competence of future primary school teachers. The pedagogical foundations of developing suggestive competence of future primary school teachers are also analyzed..

Introduction. The development of suggestive abilities in future primary school teachers enables them to express their individuality. Suggestive abilities manifest in the display of volitional qualities of both the teacher and the student, as volitional resilience forms the foundation of suggestiveness. Volitional qualities are shaped through the process of life experience and acquisition, and they represent an important practical task for every student, parent, and teacher. The capacity of the younger generation to protect themselves from harmful habits and vices, maintain their own principles and personal opinions, and overcome difficulties in educational and upbringing processes depends on the level of development of their volitional qualities. Therefore, addressing this task directly affects the effectiveness of students' current and future learning processes, as well as their participation in increasingly complex extracurricular activities.

Literature Review and Methods. The theoretical and methodological foundations, methodological systems, and challenges of developing suggestive competence in future primary school teachers have been investigated by V.A. Slastenin, G. Chijakova, I. Ridanova, H. Abdugarimov, A. Mamajonov, N. Muslimov, B. Rahimov, N. Sayidahmedov, O. Tolipov, Sh. Sharipov, N. Shodiyev, Y. Haydarov, I. Martin, A. Vett, E. Zadarko, J. Yunger, Z. Barabas, and D. Braunlar.

Results and Discussion. Suggestiveness is manifested as resilience, perseverance, and patience, rooted in an individual's inner strength. Developing such suggestive qualities in future primary school teachers lays the foundation for their success in pedagogical activities. Overall, suggestive abilities indicate the refinement and strengthening of students' academic performance and behavior. Suggestiveness is a crucial characteristic of human activity, communication, and behavior, shaping the content of life. Individuals with strong suggestive abilities demonstrate purposeful activity and consistency in behavior. Confidence in achieving

goals serves as a measure of volitional strength, as firm belief provides both physical and psychological resources to overcome difficulties. Every individual possesses opportunities to develop and cultivate suggestive will independently, and the earlier this process begins consciously, the greater the potential for success.

A review of psychological literature shows that scholars have attempted to examine suggestive abilities from various perspectives.

- Courage is the high level of self-control evident in challenging or dangerous situations, requiring resilience and determination. Moral courage in educators plays a critical role in manifesting suggestive abilities.

- Aspiration toward goals is a central factor in suggestive behavior. The more meaningful a person's goal, the more actively they pursue it. Goal-directed persistence develops suggestive competence, as suggestiveness emerges through consistent progress toward objectives.

- Self-control is another key suggestive quality, reflected in the ability to regulate one's behavior, emotions, and actions. A person with self-control can adhere to decisions, resist impulses contrary to commitments, and prevent hasty or ill-considered actions. Self-control embodies volitional strength manifested in managing behavior, emotions, activities, and social interactions.

Perseverance – the firmness of a teacher is an important means of manifesting suggestiveness. Perseverance serves as a crucial mechanism in the art of persuasion. It allows a person to mobilize their capabilities to struggle persistently with difficulties. Some problems, due to their complexity, require an individual to act calmly, seriously, and thoroughly, applying reasoning and intelligence, while others demand rapid and fair decision-making and immediate engagement to solve the task. When we observe the actions and work outcomes of determined or persevering individuals, we admire them and, in a sense, are impressed, whereas we may feel pity for those who are indecisive or lacking perseverance. Based on these reflections, the following definition can be given for this psychological concept: perseverance is the volitional quality (virtue) of an individual, expressed in the ability to quickly comprehend objective and subjective situations, evaluate them rationally, make timely, well-considered, firm, and solid decisions, and undertake their implementation without hesitation.

Discipline – is the conscious adherence of one's behavior to social norms and established rules. In pedagogical activity, suggestiveness, i.e., the art of persuasion, is carried out on the basis of strict discipline. Suggestiveness is the product of disciplined pedagogical activity.

Persistence – is the volitional trait reflecting a person's determination to implement the decisions made in a given situation, in activities, behavior, and interactions, and to strive toward achieving set goals despite the time required or certain obstacles. Persistence constitutes an essential component of suggestiveness, as the art of persuasion is based on steadfastness. Breaking through various views, ideas, theories, and stereotypes requires both suggestiveness and persistence.

Independence – is the volitional quality of a person to reach a decision through personal initiative, implement it, independently choose effective methods and approaches to apply it in

practice, and act in each task (activity) in accordance with their knowledge, skills, abilities, intellect, worldview, and beliefs.

Obligation (Execution) – a volitional trait manifested in the precise, firm, and systematic implementation of decisions.

Initiative – the ability to attempt the implementation of ideas that arise in a person.

Endurance – the ability to control emotions in various situations, maintain self-regulation, and compel oneself to perform planned actions. In developing the suggestive abilities of future primary school teachers, fostering endurance is of particular importance, as suggestive skills demand strong perseverance from the teacher.

Conclusion. The qualities described above constitute the suggestive, mental, and emotional volitional traits of an individual, demonstrating their spiritual and moral strength and capacity. In future primary school teachers, developing these suggestive abilities can enhance their pedagogical mastery. Identifying talented youth aims to stratify and individualize education, creating conditions for gifted individuals to consistently acquire fundamental and specialized knowledge at the highest level. This, in turn, establishes essential norms that should be relied upon and remembered in developing the professional and methodological training of future primary school teachers.

References:

1. Johnson Doug. The classroom teacher's technology survival guide, 2012
2. Rao Srinivas. The art of being unmistakable: A collection of yessays about making a dent in the universe, 2017
3. Spector J. Michayel. Educational technology encyclopedia of educational technology, SAGE publications, 2015
4. Schleicher Andreas. Innovation in yeducation: Lessons from pioneyers around the world, 2012